

Examining Students' Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Skill as Predictors of Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Students' mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill are strong facilitators and drive for effective learning. The study aimed to elucidate students' mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill as predictors of academic achievement in mathematics in Anambra State. Four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a predictive correlational research design. The population of the study comprised of 21204 SS II students from which a sample of 840 were drawn. Multi-stage procedure was used to select the sample. Three standardized research instruments namely; Mental Toughness Questionnaire (MTQ), Contingencies of Self-Worth Scale (CSWS) and Critical Thinking Questionnaire (CTQ) were used for data collection. Students' Mathematics Achievement Scores (SMAS) from the state wide promotion examination were used to represent mathematics achievement. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability of the items in the instruments. Reliability index were found to be .68, for mental toughness .89, for self-worth, and .74, for critical thinking skill. The data were analyzed using standard multiple regression analyses. The t-test for r , F-test and test of significance for β , were used to test hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Findings from the study showed that using mental toughness scores yielded an adjusted R squared of .008. This implies that predictors accounted for about 0.8% of the variance scores in mathematics academic achievement. Also, that mental toughness significantly predicted academic achievement scores in mathematics since their p-values are smaller than .05, while self-worth and critical thinking scores does not significantly predict academic achievement scores in mathematics since their p-values are greater than .05. Based on these findings, it was recommended that students should endorse the use of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill since the outcomes of the study have indicated that the variables relatively and jointly contributed in predicting students' academic achievement in mathematics.

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Introduction

The explanations researchers had elucidated in an attempt to understand why some students achieved academically and while others do not, are rooted in the nature of influences that have link with the non-cognitive constructs in relation with the cognitive outcomes of the students. Students success is a joint effort to engage in academic activities and satisfaction in life and there is a correlate between non-cognitive constructs and academic achievement. The present study aimed to examine if the students' mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking would predict their academic achievement of any subject domain. Dumfart and Neubauer (2016) study noted that non-cognitive variables could have an impact in the human academic development. This has not been clarified empirically in the field of educational psychology. According to Papageorgiou, Malanchini, Denovan, Clough, Shakeshaff, Schofield and Kovas (2018) several non-cognitive variables have been identified as buffers against the negative impact of stressful situations on performance in education. As a result of this, examining critical thinking, self-worth and mental toughness as variables that would relatively and jointly predict academic achievement is imperative in the educational research.

Interestingly, the study of Clough, Earle and Sewell (2002) opined that mental toughness is a personality trait that includes an array of positive characteristics such as perceiving challenge as an opportunity rather than a threat and feeling in control of life situations. This shows that mental toughness (MT), reflects an effective coping mechanism in reaction to stressors and it facilitates proactively seeking out opportunities for personal growth. Clough and colleagues (2002) characterized MT as a composite of four sub-components (the 4Cs) such as; control, commitment, challenge and confidence. In the aspect of control (life and emotion) it represents the tendency to feel and act as if one is influential and keep anxieties in check. Commitment, described the tendency to be deeply involved in pursuing goals despite difficulties that arise. In the challenge aspect of mental toughness, it deals with the tendency to see potential threats as opportunities for self-development and continue to strive in changing environments. Then confidence on its own (inabilities and interpersonal) represents the belief that one is a truly worthwhile person in spite of setbacks and the ability to push oneself forward in social setting.

Previous research has shown that MT is an important construct for explaining individual differences in learning and educational performance (McGeown, St Clar-Thompson & Clough, 2016). Then, the link that could exist among mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking to predict students' academic achievement in the mathematics domain has remained unclear in the educational research in Anambra

state. On this note, the researchers operationally defined mental toughness as the psychological construct that involves having a personal stable belief that involves seeking out challenge, wiliness to achieve, persistence and resilience in a difficult situation with high level of commitment and self-control. Then examining how MT could correlate with self-worth and critical thinking to predict academic achievement is one an interesting aspect of the study.

The paucity of empirical studies that examined the predictive nature of mental toughness, self-functioning (self-worth) and critical-thinking on students' academic achievement in mathematics necessitated to the present study. Though, relating self-worth, mental toughness and critical thinking as exogenous variables that could jointly predict academic achievement will help to discover the unique contribution of the individual variable in predicting students' academic achievement at the secondary school level. For example, the study of Garcia (2009) described self-worth as an attribute of self-esteem in which a person has staked his/her self-functioning to achieve academically. That is, the person's view of his or her value/worth depends on the perceived successes or failure to self-standards in the subject domain. This indicates that the domain of self-worth is its contingencies in the individuals' self-esteem. The study of (Garcia, 2009) previously examined self-worth in two aspects such as; external contingencies self-worth and internal contingencies self-worth. External contingencies self-worth are the contingencies that are dependent on factors that are not controlled by the individual. They include academic competence and family support. In contrast, internal contingencies self-worth depends solely on psychological processes that operate within the individual. These contingencies self-worth include virtue and God's love (Crocker & Wolter, 2001). Internal contingencies are healthier contingencies than external contingencies self-worth and are related to higher levels of being a healthy self-esteem.

The study of Crocker and Wolter discovered that contingencies self-worth (CSW) are organized by the level of importance to the individual and depending on how strong the contingency is. This shows that some contingencies will be more accessible than others. External contingencies self-worth are the less healthy contingencies and they can lead to inappropriate behaviour. Individuals whose self-worth is based on academic competence may cheat on test, or if individuals base their self-worth on approval from others, they may lie to get their approval (Crocker & Wolter, 2001). That is, when a student has a low sense of self-worth, he/she may show less wiliness and less enthusiastic to engage in learning. It could be assumed that for most students, mental toughness is based on external contingencies of self-worth. That is, when the contingencies self-worth of an individual was based upon academic competence, if he/she failed a test, the individual tend to feel worthless and his or her self-esteem plummeted (Crocker, Karpmski, Quinn & Chase, 2003). As a contingency self-worth, academic competence is at least potentially more hurtful than beneficial to the individual mostly when it is based on domain of external contingencies self-worth. External and internal contingencies self-worth are the strong attributes of self-functioning that could interact with mental toughness and critical thinking to predict academic achievement. Therefore, further explanation and empirical examination on how mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking could predict academic achievement is needed in the Nigerian educational research.

Considering the above scholarly explanations, one could have assumed that students whose self-worth is proximally and contingent with their mental toughness and critical thinking, may optimally have a relative link to predict academic achievement. On this

note, the researchers operationally defined self-worth as a healthy psychological construct that represents an attribute of self-esteem which allows individuals to fulfill their own needs for esteeming the self. Therefore, contingencies self-worth is the valuing potentialities in individuals which facilitate and describe the degree to which the individuals could base their esteemed self. These may help or hurt the desire to achieve based on the nature of contextual and personal factors that shape the individuals' desired goal.

Several theorists, therefore, concluded that students who base their self-worth on academics tend to perform well because the students strive to seek the self-esteem boosts that follow good performances and avoid the self-esteem drops that follow poor performances (Osborne, 1997). The less students base their self-worth on academics the less they tend to have this extra motivation to perform well (Major & Schmader, 1998, Steele, 1997). Another reason to expect a positive link between basing self-worth on academics and academic performance is that less successful students tend to reduce or disengage their academic contingencies of self-worth in order to protect their self-esteem (Major & Schmader, 1998). Other theorists propose that students who base their self-worth on academics actually risk underperforming (Burhans & Dweck, 1995). These theorists observed that although basing self-worth on academics can be motivating. It can also increase pressure, which can reduce intrinsic motivation, increase ability-validation goals and anxiety, and impair self-regulation.

The scholarly reviews seem to suggest that academic contingencies of self-worth can impair achievement in variety of academic settings. A more nuanced view is that students with high basing of self-worth on academics are at risk of underperforming in academic settings that emphasize evaluation rather than learning (Major & Schmader, 1998). Although, achievement motivation research shows that students, in general, tend to underperform in the former compare to the latter settings (Utman, 1997). The study of Molden and Dweck (2000) proposed that students who base their self-worth on academics are especially vulnerable to this performance pattern. The study of Lawrence and Crocker (2009) found that when students thought they were taking a test that measured ability, the more they base their self-worth on academics, the worse their test performance. Considering the relative contributions of on the influence of self-worth on academic achievement, examining its link with critical thinking of the students to predict academic achievement is another aim of the present study.

Critical thinking skill has been defined as being aware of one's own thought process and what one is trying to do or achieve (Andolina, 2002). It involved reflecting upon what has happened and considering how to improve it. Elder and Paul (2010) noted that in the process of going from an unreflective thinking to an accomplished thinking, a person moves from being unaware of their own thinking to being highly in tune with their thoughts and always seeking to refine and clarify them. Also, reflective thinking is one form of critical thinking skill and this has led to confusion among many scholars. The expansion of knowledge on this construct has made Hajrezahi, Roshani and Shahalizade (2015) to define critical thinking skill as a purposeful self-supervised judgment process that reflects the thinking process of interpretation, reasoning, analysis and evaluation. That is, the acquisition of a variety of skills such as; mental toughness, critical thinking skill, problem-solving skills, communication skills and collaborating skills could impact positively on academic achievement if the self-worth of the individual is positively developed. This is because the 21st century environment

requires a generation of critical thinkers with balanced mental capacity and highly organized self in problem solving. This described people that can participate actively in taking decisions on local and global issues that could emerged through a thought process.

The thinking process is an activity that involves the work of the brain, feelings and human mind which can be seen through learning that focuses on student academic activities. In the process of critical thinking skill, individuals make connections between objects that are the main problem with the parts of knowledge they already have. Norris and Ennis (1989) revealed stages that include the process of critical thinking skill. The first is to clarify the issue by asking questions, the second is gather information about the issue, the third is starting the reasoning through various side or different point of view and the forth is gathering information and conduct further analysis. This is an indication that 21st century learning requires everyone to learn and think, focusing on developing intellectual abilities so that they can adapt to changes in the learning environment. The skills are the ability to synthesize information, work as a team, manage broadly and complex and be responsible to the community and environment (Balasubramanian, Jaykumar & Fukey, 2014). In respect to the scholar's contributions, the researchers operationally defined critical thinking as a thinking process that involves the objective analysis and evaluation of an idea in order to form a judgement. Then, assuming that critical thinking skill may have link with mental toughness and self-worth to influence students' learning behavior also need to be clarified through the empirical findings in the present study. Perhaps, it will help to ascertain the fitness of the three variable to jointly predict academic achievement scores in mathematics.

Academic achievement has been defined as scores obtained from examining the extent to which a person has acquired certain information or mastering certain skills, in the process of learning within the classroom (Meherns & Lehman, 2008). These scores characterized the academic outcome obtained from achievement test designed to assess a person's performance in a course of study which he/she has undergone. These can be regular performance feedback obtained by means of standardized test scores as presented by the approved examination board. Then, the researchers operationally defined academic achievement as the cognitive outcome that described the level at which the students had engaged and mastered the instructional skills that have impacted on them within a specific learning period. Suffice it to say that many studies have examined the relationship between critical thinking skill and academic achievement. Though no known study has empirically or theoretically examined students' mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skills as determinant of students' academic achievement in Anambra State.

The study of Erwin and Muhsin (2020) revealed that there is a link between the students' critical thinking skill and their cognitive realm in English test. In the study of Nur'azizah, Utani, and Hastuti (2020) it was recorded that a positive and significant relationship existed between students' critical thinking skill and academic achievement. The study of Taghva, Rezaei, Ghaderiand and Taghva (2014) revealed a significant relationship between critical thinking skill and students' academic achievement. Emesi and Anyanwu (2023) recorded a significant relationship between students' critical thinking skill and their academic achievement in mathematics. Also, the study of Anyanwu, Ezenwosu and Emesi and Eleje (2022) recorded that the seven assumptions tested were fit for the study. Also, that the regression model using mental toughness, narcissism and self-worth scores was significant in predicting achievement scores

followed by mental toughness scores. Their study also indicated that the unique contribution of the variables significantly predicts academic achievement scores in mathematics. The value of the effect size of the variables in explaining the unique contribution using R adjusted square .002 indicates a minimal effect. On this note, it was indicated that self-worth recorded the highest predictor of academic achievement among other variables. Therefore, the paucity of study elucidated the possible association of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill in predicting students' academic achievement in Anambra State, had created an avenue for the present study. On this back drop, the study examined mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill as predictors of academic achievement in mathematics in Anambra State Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are the assumptions of multiple regression equation for predicting students' academic achievement scores in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores met?
2. What is the nature of the regression equation for predicting students' academic achievement scores in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores?
3. What is the unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics?
4. Which of the independent variables predicts students' academic achievement scores in mathematics?

Hypotheses

1. The regression equation does not significantly predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores.
2. The unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics is not significant.
3. Mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores do not significantly predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics.

Research Method

The researchers adopted a predictive correlational research design and used questionnaires to collect data for the study. The population of this study consisted of 21204 which represented all the senior secondary school students II in Anambra State. A sample of 840 SS2 students was drawn from the senior secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra State. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the respondents. The procedures for the selection were as follows: In stage one, three education zones were selected from the six education zones in the state by simple random sampling. Then in stage two, from each sampled education zone, one local government area (L.G.A) was selected through simple random sampling given a total of three (3) L.G.As. In stage three, from each sampled L.G.A, 10 schools were randomly selected giving a total of 30 schools. Then, from each of the schools, 28

students were selected for the study using purposive sampling. This gave a total number of 840 students used in the study.

The study adapted three standardized research questionnaires namely, Tabachnick and Fidell (2001) Mental Toughness Questionnaire, (MTQ), Abedi Creativity Test Questionnaire (1993) (ACTQ) and Crocker, Luhtanen, Cooper and Bouvrette (2003) Contingencies of Self-Worth Scale (CSWS). The students' achievement scores were obtained from that state wide Senior Secondary One (SS1) promotion examination from the schools before the administration of the instruments. The methods used for validating the instruments were face and construct validity by the three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. Cronbach's alpha reliability method was used to determine the internal consistency of the sub-scales for the three instruments were such as; mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking were .68, .89, and .74 respectively. The data were analyzed using standard multiple regression analyses. The t-test for r , F-test and test of significance for β , were used to test hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The data were first screened for missing values, and 38 respondents had missing representing 4.5%. Hence likewise deletion approach was adopted. After deleting the 38 respondents, the sample size was reduced to 802. Thereafter, analysis of the study was carried out using standard multiple regression analysis with SPSS 26.

Research Question 1

To what extent are the assumptions of the regression equation for predicting students' academic achievement in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth, and critical thinking skills scores met?

Table 1. Correlation and descriptive statistics of independent and dependent variables in the regression model for this study (N = 802)

Variables	M.T	SW	CT	Ach	X	SD	VAR	SK	KU	TF	VIF
MT	1				22.44	3.230	10.431	.205	-.672	.928	1.078
SW	.258	1			22.29	3.281	10.766	.228	-.518	.926	1.080
CT	-.101	-.111	1		54.54	8.230	67.732	-.059	-.392	.982	1.018
Ach	-.096	-.009	.119	1	58.32	8.299	68.881	.139	-.625	-----	-----

Note: Std. Residual Min = -2.886, Std. residual Max = 3.053, Durbin Waston statistics = 1.908; MT = Mental Toughness, SW = Self-Worth, CT = Critical Thinking skills and Ach = Academic Achievement.

Figure 1. The Normal P.P Plot of Standardized Residuals Data Points of Academic Achievement

Figure 2. The Normal Distribution Curve of Standardized Residuals Data Points of Academic Achievement

Figure 3. The Scatter Plot of Standardized Residuals Data Points of Academic Achievement

To answer research question 1, seven assumptions of multiple linear regression were tested in this study. First, the assumptions of normality of the data were tested using Skewness and Kurtosis. The assumptions were made since none of the Skewness and Kurtosis values of each of the variables do not exceed + 3 and – 3 as recommended. Second, the assumptions of absence of multivariate outliers was checked using standardized residual statistics and Cook's distance statistics (1977). Result of standardized residual values indicated that the (Std, Residual Min = -2.886, Std, Residual Max = 3.053). It lies between -3 to 3 as recommended by (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2018). While the result of the Cook's distance shows a maximum value of .014 which is less than 1 as recommended by (Cook, 1977). Hence, the assumptions of absence of multivariate outliers was not violated. Third, the assumptions of absence of multicollinearity among the predicting variables were checked using Variance Inflated Factor (VIF), and Tolerance Factor (TF). The Tolerance Factors and Variance Inflated Factors (Mental toughness, TF = .928, VIF = 1.078; Self-worth, TF = .926, VIF = 1.080; Critical thinking skill, TF = .982, VIF = 1.018; of the independent

variables show that the values were less than 10 for Variance Inflated Factor and greater than .20 for Tolerance Factor respectively as recommended by (Schumaker, 2015). Hence, this assumption of absence of multicollinearity was made. Forth, the assumption of independent of error was tested using Durbin Waston statistics. The result shown a Durbin Waston statistics of 1.908 which is less than 3 but greater than 0 as recommended by (Denis, 2020). Hence, the assumption of independent of error was not violated. Fifth, the assumptions of normality of error distribution were tested using normal P.P plot of standardized residual. Figure 1 shows that the normal P.P plot of standardized residual data points were normally distributed. Histogram of the standardized residual in figure 2 also testified to that. Sixth, the assumption of homogeneity of variance and linearity was tested using scatter plot of standardized predicted values. The result in figure 3 shows that the data met the assumption of homogeneity of variance and linearity as the predicted values were distributed above zero in both dimensions and do not show any pattern. Seventh, the assumptions of non-zero variance were tested using variance statistics and the data also met the assumptions of non-zero variances (Mental toughness, Variance = 10.431; Self-worth, Variance = 10.766; Critical thinking skill, Variance = 7.959; Low self-esteem, Variance = 67.732; Academic achievement, Variance = 68.881) as there is no zero variance for the variables in the study as shown in the table 1.

Research Question 2

What is the nature of the regression equation for predicting students' academic achievement scores in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores?

Table 2. Regression Coefficient for Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Scores (N = 802)

Model	Unstandardized Beta	Std. Error	Standardized Beta
Constant	60.120	3.429	
Mental toughness	-.250	.094	-.097
Self-worth	.053	.092	.021
Critical thinking skill	.048	.036	.048

Using the information in table 2, the nature of the regression equation for predicting students' academic achievement in mathematics using academic mental toughness, self-worth, and critical thinking skill scores follows:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2 x_2 + b_3 x_3$$

$$Y = 60.120 + -.250 x_1 + .053 x_2 + .048 x_3$$

$$Ach = 60.120 - 0.258 + 0.106 + 0.144$$

$$Achievement = 60.120 - 0.258MT + 0.106SW + 0.144CT$$

MT = Mental Toughness, SW = Self-Worth, CT = Critical Thinking. The equation shows that for every unit decrease in mental toughness, achievement decreased by -0.258. For every unit increase in self-worth, achievement increased by 0.106. For every unit increase in critical thinking skill, achievement increased by 0.144.

Research Question 3

What is the unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics?

Table 3. Regression Model Summary of Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Skills Scores to Predict Students' Academic Achievement Scores in Mathematics (N = 802)

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.109 ^a	.012	.008	8.266

To answer this research, question the adjusted multiple regression R square was used. The result of study shows that using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores yielded an adjusted R squared of .008. This implies that predictors accounted for about 0.8% of the variance scores in mathematics academic achievement.

Research Question 4

Which of the independent variables best predicted students' academic achievement scores in mathematics?

Table 4. Regression Coefficient for Students' Academic Achievement Scores in Mathematics Using Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Skill Scores (N = 802)

Model	Unstandardized Beta	Std. Error	Standardized Beta
Constant	60.120	3.429	
Mental toughness	-.250	.094	-.097
Self-worth	.053	.092	.021
Critical thinking skill	.048	.036	.048

Table 4: Regression coefficient for students' academic achievement scores in mathematics using mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores. To answer this research question 4, the standardized regression coefficient (B) in table 4 was used for comparison. The regression coefficients presented in table 4 shows unstandardized (B) and standardized regression coefficient (B) mental toughness scores are -.250 and -.097. For self-worth scores are 053 and .021. For critical thinking skill scores are .048 and .048 respectively. Using the standardized beta for comparison, critical thinking is mostly predicted students' academic achievement in mathematics as shown by the B of .048. Self-worth is the second most predicted students' academic achievement in mathematics as shown by the B of .021. While mental toughness is the least predicted students' academic achievement in mathematics as shown by the B of -.097.

Hypothesis 1

The regression model does not significantly predict academic achievement scores in mathematics.

The analysis of variance in the table shows that the regression equation was significant (3, 798) = 3.173, $p < .05$. This implies that at least one of the independent variables significantly predicted the academic achievement in mathematics.

Table 5. F-Test for Regression Model of Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Skill Scores on Students' Academic Achievement Scores in Mathematics (N = 802)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	650.356	3	216.785	3.173	.024 ^b
Residual	54523.355	798	68.325		
Total	55173.711	801			

Hypothesis 2

The unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to students' academic achievement scores to predict academic achievement scores in mathematics is not statistically significant.

Table 6. T-Test of Adjusted R Square of the Regression Model for This Study (N = 802)

Model	R	R- Square	Adjusted R- Square	Std. Error Estimate	t – cal for adj. R ²	DF	t- crt.	Remark
	.109 ^a	.012	.008	8.266	88.3694	801	1.960	S

To test hypothesis 2, t-test for adjusted R square was conducted. Results of the study shown in table 6 indicates that t-critical for adjusted R square is 1.960 while that of the t-calculated is 88.3694. Since the t-calculated for adjusted R square 88.3694 is greater than t-critical 1.960, the null hypothesis which states that the unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to students' academic achievement scores to predict students' academic achievement in mathematics scores is not statistically significant is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. In other words, the unique contributions of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores to predict students' academic achievement scores is statistically significant. Effect sizes were also evaluated using adjusted R² comparing it with Cohen's *d* statistics guideline, where $d < 0.20$ indicates a minimal effects size, $0.20 < d < 0.50$ indicates a small effect size, $0.50 < d < 0.80$ indicates a moderate effect size, and $d > 0.80$ indicates a large effect size. The value of R adjusted square .008 indicates a small effect size.

Hypothesis 3

Mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill scores does not significantly predict students' academic achievement scores in mathematics.

Table 7. T-Test of Regression Coefficient of Students' Academic Achievement Scores in Mathematics Using Mental Toughness, Self-Worth and Critical Thinking Skill Scores (N = 802)

Model	Unstandardized Beta	Std. Error	Standardized B	P-value	Remark
Constant	60.120	3.429		.000	S
Mental toughness	-.250	.094	-.097	.008	S
Self-worth	.053	.092	.021	.564	NS
Critical thinking skill	.048	.036	.048	.181	NS

Table 7 shows that mental toughness significantly predicted academic achievement scores in mathematics since their p-values are smaller than .05. While self-worth and critical thinking skill scores does not significantly predict academic achievement scores in mathematics since their p-values are greater than .05.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the study indicated that the seven assumptions that were tested did not violate the statistical guides being consulted in process of checking the assumptions. This is an indication that the mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking are potentially fit to examine students' motivational propensity to respond and achieve academically. This supported the findings from the study of Anyanwu, Ezenwosu and Emesi (2022) which recorded that the seven assumptions that were tested in the study which involved mental toughness, self-worth and narcissism were statistically fit for their study. Meeting the assumptions of the regression model implies that the data are suitable and amenable for the analysis. This implies that results obtained from the multiple regression analysis are more precise, accurate and reliable in predicting academic achievement in mathematics.

The findings from the result revealed that on the nature of regression equation, self-worth and critical thinking skill contributed positively to the predicting the regression model. While the mental toughness has negative contribution to the predicting model. This implies that self-worth and critical thinking skill have certain level of influence on students' academic achievement scores in mathematics. The findings partially supported the study of Anyanwu *et al* (2022) which recorded that self-worth positively contributed in predicting the regression model while mental toughness negatively contributed in predicting the regression model.

In the present study, the result revealed that using multiple regression R square stands to prove a dynamic relationship among mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill as they jointly predict achievement scores in mathematics. The small percentage (0.8%) of these variables in predicting academic achievement scores indicated that the constructs are salient predictors of learning outcomes in mathematics. This supported the study of Anyanwu *et al* (2022) which revealed that mental toughness and self-worth jointly predict academic achievement with the small percentage of (0.2%).

Findings from the study also indicate that the independent variables have roles to play on students' academic achievement in mathematics. For example, when students' level of mental toughness is negatively low, their level of willingness to adjust and engage in learning of mathematics will be negatively low. Also, when students' level of critical thinking and self-worth is positively low, level of constructive reasoning in solving mathematics problems will positively low in learning mathematics. This partially supported the study of Anyanwu *et al* (2022) which revealed that mental toughness was negatively low in predicting students' mathematics scores, while self-worth was positively low in determining their academic achievement.

Finding in the study using effect sizes to evaluate using adjusted R^2 to compare it with Cohen's d statistics guideline, the value of R adjusted square .008 indicates a minimal effect. This shows that academic achievement is decreasing considering the motivational constructs being tested in the present study. It is an indication that there

is students' motivational apathy to respond, adjust and engage in the learning task as well as achieving academically as the variables jointly predict mathematics achievement scores. This supported the finding from the study of Anyanwu *et al* (2022) which revealed that the value of R adjusted square .002 as it indicates a minimal effect.

Conclusion

The outcome of the present study unveiled that the analysis of variance recorded that the regression equation was significant. This implies that mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill jointly and statistically predicted students' academic achievement in mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should endorse the use of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill since the outcomes of the study have indicated that the variables relatively and jointly contributed in predicting students' academic achievement in mathematics.
2. Teachers should also encourage the students to make use of mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill in their learning process since the association among the variables was significant in predicting academic achievement.
3. On this note, parents should advice the children to start developing their mental toughness, self-worth and critical thinking skill in a positive dimension as constructs that have the potentialities to influence positive behavioural outcome mostly in the context that involves life goal achievement.
4. Finally, current researchers in the field of educational psychology should adopt other research designs such as comparative correlation design and hierarchical predictive research design to revisit these variables either within the same academic context or other context such as higher institution perspective.

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